

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF IMPACT PERFORMANCE FOR PMI FOAM FILLED CORRUGATED BOARD SANDWICH STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

The sandwich structures have the advantages of light weight, high strength and strong versatility. It is widely used in various fields such as aerospace, civil engineering, marine engineering. Among them, the corrugated sandwich structure has the advantages of high specific stiffness and specific strength. It has significant advantages in terms of explosion resistance and impact resistance. PMI has higher strength than other foamed polymers and has the advantage of low density. Since PMI has good formability, this paper fills it into corrugated sandwich structure to form a PMI sandwich structure. Then, an impact resistance analysis of the sandwich structure was performed. First, the structure is modeled by Solidworks software. This paper uses LS-DYNA to numerically simulate the sandwich structure of Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar impact PMI filled corrugated plate. This paper obtained the stress-strain curve and energy of the incident bar and the transition bar. This method is used to verify the impact resistance of the sandwich structure. In this paper the same size panels and core density were used. Meanwhile, five different striker velocities and different fiber layers were applied as variables. The Hopkinson bar impacted the sandwich structure for simulation. Finally, the impact resistance of PMI-filled corrugated sheets is obtained.

1 INTRODUCTION

The sandwich structure has high strength and high stiffness mechanical properties under the same weight, and has been widely used in aerospace, civil engineering and ship protection. In the conventional sandwich structure, a foam sandwich structure and a periodic arrangement sandwich structure such as a honeycomb sandwich structure, a corrugated sandwich structure and a grid structure are included.

Among them, the corrugated sandwich structure is widely used because of its good manufacturing process and mechanical properties. Many people have studied the static and dynamic mechanical properties of corrugated sandwich structures.

Mohammadi et al. proposed an analytical equivalent model that can be used to predict the mechanical properties of a trapezoidal core corrugated sandwich structures [1]. Cao B.T. studied the mechanical response of multi-stage corrugated plates during low-speed impact. The impact resistance and equivalent dynamic constitutive model of a multi-stage corrugated board were measured by the Hopkinson test

[2].Rubino et al. studied the quasi-static three-point bending displacement response of a corrugated sandwich structure of a Y-shaped core and a triangular core under simple support and fixed support [3].Zhang et al. studied some mechanical properties of trapezoidal corrugated sandwich composite structures, such as bending strength, stiffness and energy absorption [4].

Polymethacrylimide foam is fully closed-cell isotropic foam which possesses high stiffness and strength to weight ratios. The first application of polymethyl methacrylate as a core sandwich structure was in 1971 as a helicopter fuselage panel [5]. The PMI foam is composed of a copolymer of methyl methacrylate (MAA) and methacrylonitrile (MAN). The foam has good chemical stability and high deformation temperature and exhibits good mechanical properties. It is widely used as a sandwich core material.

Corrugated sandwich structure and PMI foam show excellent performance in terms of impact resistance and energy absorption . Therefore , this study combines the advantages of both to design a pmi-filled corrugated sandwich structure .In this study, the effect of these amounts on the dynamic mechanical properties of the sandwich structure was studied by changing the speed of strick in SHPB, the density of pmi, and the number of layers of fiberboard.

2 NUMERICAL SIMULATION

2.1 BRIEF INTRODUCTION OF SANDWICH STRUCTURE MODEL

The mechanical behavior of the PMI-filled corrugated sandwich structure under low-speed impact is numerically simulated. As shown in Fig. 1, the main body of the sandwich structure is a corrugated board, which is mainly composed of a corrugated core and a panel.

Figure 1: Trapezoidal corrugated sandwich structure

Parameter	Significance
d_1	Trapezoidal upper base length
d_2	Trapezoidal lower base length
t	Trapezoidal corrugated core thickness

Table 1: Significance for each Parameter

The dimensions of the corrugated core are as follows : $d_1 = 4$ mm, $d_2 = 15$ mm, $t = 1$ mm. The meaning of the symbols is shown in Table 1. The panels are made of fiberglass and each layer has a thickness of 0.2 mm. In this paper, the mechanical properties and energy absorption properties of the

panels at 5 layers, 6 layers and 7 layers are investigated. In this paper, PMI is filled into the corrugated plate to enhance the energy absorbing performance of the sandwich structure.

As shown in Figure 2, the Hopkinson experimental model consists of a striker, an incident rod, a test piece and a transmission rod. After the striker is accelerated, it collides with the incident bar. a pulse is formed on the incident bar to provide a compressive load to the test piece. Through the one-dimensional elastic wave assumption and the impact dynamics theory, the dynamic stress and strain of the specimen during the impact can be obtained. Through the simulation results, the dynamic mechanical properties and energy absorption characteristics of the test piece can be analyzed.

Figure 2: the split Hopkinson pressure bar experimental device

As shown in Fig. 3, by establishing a full scale model, this paper uses numerical simulation of the sandwich structure. The length of the striker is 600mm, and the length of the incident bar and the transmission bar are both 3300mm. In the modeling process, the element system adopted is shown in Table 2. Considering the existence of force and torque during the impact process, the model grid type in this paper uses Soild164 element. By the length of the striker, the incident bar, and the transmission bar, each element of the striker, incident bar and transmission bar have a radial dimension of 3 mm and an axial dimension of 10 mm. Since the test piece undergoes large displacement nonlinear deformation during the impact process, the element size is 1 mm.

Figure 3: Hopkinson bar impact model

In this paper, four material models are defined: Q235 steel material model, aluminum material model, PMI material model, and fiberglass panel material model.

PHYSICAL QUANTITY	ELEMENT
LENGTH	m
TIME	s
FORCE	N
MASS	kg

Table 2: Model element correspondence table

The striker, the incident bar and the transmission bar are made of MAT 001-ELASTIC material model of Q235 steel. The size of the three bars is larger than the size of the test piece. Therefore, using the linear elastic model does not affect the accuracy of the simulation. Since the model only contains mass and elastic parameters, the one-dimensional stress wave hypothesis in the Hopkinson rod is established, which can more accurately show the mechanical behavior of the specimen under low velocity impact. The parameters of the bar are as follows: density is 7850 kg/m³; Poisson's ratio is 0.33; elastic modulus is 200 GPa.

MAT 53-CLOSED CELL FOAM material model was used for PMI, which has the effect of air pressure in the cell body and pores under pressure and better simulate the properties of PMI. The stress of the foam model is:

$$\sigma_{ij} = \sigma_{ij}^{sk} + \delta_{ij}[P_0\gamma/(1 + \gamma - \Phi)] \quad (2-1)$$

Here, σ_{ij}^{sk} is the profile stress, P_0 is the initial closed gas pressure of the foam, δ_{ij} is Kronecker delta, Φ is the ratio of the density of the foam to the matrix, and γ is the volumetric strain.

the MAT 022-COMPOSITE DAMAGE material model in LS-DYNA was used for the panel to define the parameters of the glass.

During the impact, the buckling deformation of the core absorbs energy. Therefore, MAT 003-PLASTIC KINEMATIC model is used to simulate the mechanical behavior of the core during the impact process. Where: density is 2700kg/m³; Elastic modulus is 70 GPa; Poisson's ratio is 0.33; Yield strength is 455 MPa; Tangent modulus is 26 GPa.

2.2 SHPB Low Velocity Impact

2.2.1 Mechanical response at different striker speed

In this paper, the energy absorption characteristics of the sample under low velocity impact were obtained by simulating the Hopkinson pressure bar experiment. In the Hopkinson data processing, the dynamic stress strain of the test piece is obtained by analyzing the reflected wave and the transmitted wave, as shown in the formula (2-2).

$$\begin{cases} \sigma = \frac{AE}{A_0} \varepsilon_t \\ \varepsilon = -\frac{2c_0}{l_0} \int_0^t \varepsilon_r dt \\ \dot{\varepsilon} = -\frac{2c_0}{l_0} \varepsilon_r \end{cases} \quad (2-2)$$

Here, c_0 is elastic wave velocity in the pressure bar, ε_i is strain in the bar corresponding to the incident wave when it propagates independently, ε_r is the strain in the bar corresponding to the reflected

wave during independent propagation, ϵ_i is the strain in the bar corresponding to the transmitted wave when it propagates independently, l_0 is length of test piece

According to the hopkinson correlation theory, the strain rate is determined by the velocity of the striker. Therefore, the conclusions drawn from the analysis of different striker speeds are also studying the effect of strain rate on the test piece. There is a positive correlation between bullet velocity and strain rate. This paper studies the mechanical response of the sandwich structure under the velocity of 7m/s, 8m/s and 9m/s striker. The effects of strain rate on dynamic constitutive and energy absorption characteristics are obtained

A element of the center of the incident bar and the center of the transmission bar is selected to extract the stress of the element, as shown in Fig.4 and Fig.5.

Figure 4: Incident reflected wave curve at different striker speeds

Figure 5: Transmission wave curve at different striker speeds

From the figure, the average peak value of the incident wave corresponding to the striker velocity of 7m/s, 8m/s, and 9m/s is 43.1Mpa, 49.3Mpa, and 55.5Mpa. The peak values of the reflected waves corresponding to the speed of the three types of strikers are 32.9 MPa, 38.7 MPa, and 44.5 MPa. After passing the test piece, the stress peaks of the transmitted wave were 15.1 MPa, 15.4 MPa, and 15.6 MPa. Compared with the striker speed of 7m/s, the striker speed of 8m/s and 9m/s increased by 14.28% and 28.57%. The peak value of the transmitted wave only increased by 1.99% and 3.31%. Therefore, during the low speed impact, different striker speeds have less influence on the impact resistance of the test piece.

Figure 6: Stress-strain curves at different striker speeds

After processing the data of the simulation results, the stress-strain curves at different striker speeds are obtained, as shown in Fig.6. After the striker collides with the incident rod, the test piece is loaded in the form of a pulse in the incident bar. In the initial stage, the sandwich structure is subjected to the overall load, the PMI is compressed, the aluminum core begins to buckle and the time-stress curve appears as a linear elastic phase. When the stress reaches the peak, it begins to decrease. at this time, the PMI foam local element cell begins to collapse. The peak stress corresponding to 7m/s is 31.7 Mpa. The peak stress corresponding to 8m/s is 32.4 Mpa. The peak stress corresponding to 9m/s is 33.0 Mpa

Striker Speed (m/s)	7	8	9
Energy (J)	23.033	28.789	34.960

Table 3: Energy absorbed at different striker speeds

The energy absorption characteristics of the core in the low-speed impact process are divided into two types, one is PMI compression fracture energy absorption, another is aluminum buckling core buckling deformation energy absorption. As shown in Table 3, the energy data is presented from the simulation results. and the energy absorbed at 7m/s, 8m/s, and 9m/s is 23.033J, 28.789J, and 34.960J, respectively

2.2.2 Mechanical response at different density of PMI

In this paper, two kinds of densities of 52kg/m³ and 72kg/m³ were selected for numerical simulation. By processing the simulation data, the stress-strain curve is obtained as shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 7: Stress-strain curves at different PMI densities

Among them, the ultimate stress at PMI density of 52kg / m³ and 72kg / m³ is 29.07Mpa and 31.7Mpa, respectively. By comparing the curves, it was found that the dynamic limit stress decreased by 8.30% when the PMI density in the core layer decreased by 28%. After the density is reduced, the pressure of the gas released by the crushing of the element cell is small. However, since the compressive strength of aluminum in the core is large, the change of the dynamic limit stress is not so obvious.

Density of PMI(kg/m ³)	52	72
Energy (J)	16.800	23.033

Table 4: Energy absorbed at different PMI densities

As shown in Table 4, the energy absorbed by the core at PMI density of 52 kg/m³ and 72 kg/m³ were 16.8 J and 23.033 J, respectively. When the density decreased by 28%, the energy absorption effect decreased by 27%. After the density is reduced, the pressure of the gas released by the crushing of the element cell is small. And the energy that can be stored in each element cell body also decreases, so the energy absorption effect is reduced.

2.2.3 Mechanical response at different number of panel layers

Figure 8: Stress-strain curves for different panel layers

Number of layers	5	6	7
Energy (J)	23.023	23.448	23.033

Table 5: Energy absorbed by different layers

In this paper, the sandwich structures under the 5 layers, 6 layers and 7 layers panels are numerically simulated. Each layer's thickness is 0.2 mm. The stress-strain curve is obtained by analyzing the simulation results, as shown in Fig. 8. The dynamic ultimate stress of sandwich structures composed of 5 layer panels, 6 layer panels and 7 layer panels during low-speed impact is 31.6Mpa.

From the numerical simulation results, the internal energy of each component in the core is extracted. and the energy absorption of the sandwich structure of different layers is obtained, as shown in Table 5. Among them, the energy absorbed by the sandwich structure of 5 layer panels, 6 layer panels, and 7 layer panels is 23.023J, 23.448J, and 23.033J, respectively. The energy absorbed by each sandwich

structure during low-speed impact is very small. Therefore, in the case of low speed impact, the number of panel layers has little effect on the energy absorption effect of the sandwich structure.

3 CONCLUSIONS

(1) Compared with the 7m/s striker speed, the striker speed of 8m/s and 9m/s increased by 14.28% and 28.57%. The peak value of the transmitted wave only increased by 1.99% and 3.31%.

(2) The energy absorbed by the sandwich structure at 7m/s, 8m/s, and 9m/s is 23.033J, 28.789J, and 34.960J, respectively.

(3) The ultimate stresses corresponding to 52kg/m³ and 72kg/m³ are 29.07Mpa and 31.7Mpa, respectively.

(4) The energy absorbed by the core at a PMI density of 52 kg/m³ and 72 kg/m³ was 16.8 J and 23.033 J, respectively. When the density decreased by 28%, the energy absorption effect decreased by 27%.

(5) The dynamic ultimate stress of sandwich structures composed of 5 layer panels, 6 layer panels and 7 layer panels during low-speed impact is 31.6Mpa.

(6) The energy absorbed by the sandwich structure of the 5 layer panels, 6 layer panels and 7 layer panels is 23.023J, 23.448J, and 23.033J, respectively.

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REFERENCES

- [1] H. Mohammadi, S. Ziaei-Rad, I. Dayyani. Thomsen, An equivalent model for trapezoidal corrugated cores based on homogenization method, *Composite Structures*, 131, 1 November 2015, pp. 160-170 (doi : [10.1016/j.compstruct.2015.04.048](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2015.04.048)) .
- [2] B. T. Cao, B. Hou, Y. L. Li, H. Zhao, An experimental study on the impact behavior of multilayer sandwich with corrugated cores, *International Journal of Solids and Structures*, 109, 2017, pp. 33-45(doi : [10.1016/j.ijsolstr.2017.01.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijsolstr.2017.01.005).)
- [3] V. Rubino, V. S. Deshpande, N. A. Fleck, The three-point bending of Y-frame and corrugated core sandwich beams, *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences*, 52, 2010, pp. 485-494 (doi: [10.1016/j.ijmecsci.2009.11.009](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmecsci.2009.11.009)).
- [4] Pan Zhang, Jun Liu, Yuansheng Cheng, Hailiang Hou, Yong Li, Dynamic response of metallic trapezoidal corrugated-core sandwich panels subjected to air blast loading – An experimental study, *Materials & Design* (1980-2015), 65, 2015, pp. 221-230 (doi: [10.1016/j.matdes.2014.08.071](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matdes.2014.08.071)).
- [5] Jia Qu, Dianwei Ju, Shenrou Gao, Jiawei Chen, Research on the dynamic mechanical properties of polymethacrylimide foam sandwich structure, *Composite Structures*, 204, 2018, pp. 22-30 (doi: [10.1016/j.compstruct.2018.07.078](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2018.07.078)).